

Factors Affecting Reading Literacy Skills of Junior High School Learners

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Abstract:

The study focused on the Degree of Factors Affecting Reading Literacy Skills of Junior High School Learners. There were 42 teachers who were utilized as respondents in this study and conducted at Sofronio Carmona Memorial National High School, Don Salvador Benedicto, Negros Occidental. Based on the research-made survey questionnaire, the degree of factors affecting reading literacy skills of junior high school had a high degree with the presence of variables such as age, sex, average family monthly income, and highest educational attainment. To determine this result, the mean and frequency count and percentage were utilized in analyzing the data taken from the survey questionnaire. Based on the findings of this study, the degree of factors affecting reading literacy skills of junior high school learners were found to be high in all areas; fluency, vocabulary and comprehension. And no significant difference was found when respondents were grouped according to these variables. It was revealed that; teachers play a significant role in the acquisition of literacy skills among learners. Teachers' motivation and effective use of learning materials can significantly impact the fluency and comprehension skills of learners. Furthermore, it is recommended that school administrators must offer suitable trainings and seminars for teachers especially to those who are teaching reading literacy skills among learners and provide them with technical assistance when it comes to new technological tools which are really important in teaching learners of this generation.

Keywords: Junior High School, Learners, reading literacy skills

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Literacy is broadly defined as the ability to read, write, speak, and listen in a language, with a particular focus on reading and writing at a level that allows individuals to effectively communicate and participate in society. Reading literacy is seen as essential for full societal participation, as it enables individuals to integrate prior knowledge, critically evaluate information, and assess the validity of arguments (PISA, 2018). Moreover, reading literacy plays a vital role in strengthening a nation's cultural influence and social development, acting as a key indicator of a country's competitiveness and progress. Identifying factors that affect reading literacy is crucial for improving educational policies, curriculum design, and teaching strategies, as literate individuals are better equipped to make informed decisions, solve problems, and engage in their communities (Luo et al., 2016).

This research examines the factors influencing learners' reading literacy skills as a foundation for developing an intervention plan. The pandemic has severely impacted students' reading abilities, with many struggling to comprehend texts, perform poorly in assessments, and miss academic milestones. These challenges have led to feelings of frustration and discouragement, contributing to high dropout rates, increased absenteeism, and long-term negative effects on their academic and personal growth. Addressing these issues through targeted interventions is essential for supporting students in developing the reading literacy skills necessary for lifelong success.

As a reading teacher, the researcher encounters many students having difficulties in reading, particularly in the early stage of junior high school, grade 7, and other grade levels. Some students lack fluency because they are struggling with decoding words. Still, other students lack fluency because they do not connect meaning to the words they read. Regarding vocabulary, some students find it difficult to pronounce words, write and spell, and use grammatical patterns correctly. Meanwhile, some learners struggle with comprehension, critical thinking skills, and reading materials. This study could help the learners and teachers determine the effective teaching strategy and, of course, the parents so that they would know how to do follow-ups at home.

Current State of Knowledge

Reading literacy is essential for effective written communication in various contexts, including education, entertainment, and communication. It goes beyond technical reading skills to encompass comprehension, evaluation, and application of written information (Hemmerechts et al., 2017). A strong reading foundation is vital for students to achieve academic success and fully participate in society, which also contributes to national competitiveness and cultural influence (Lou et al., 2016). Key components of reading literacy include fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension. Reading fluency, which involves accuracy, speed, and prosody, plays a critical role in academic performance, while vocabulary knowledge is a significant barrier to comprehension, especially for second-language learners (Alqahtani, 2015). Reading comprehension, a complex process that involves multiple cognitive and linguistic components, is closely linked to fluency and academic outcomes (Meniado, 2016; Álvarez-Cañizo et al., 2015). Moreover, students' interest in reading can enhance their vocabulary acquisition, as more enthusiastic readers tend to develop stronger vocabulary skills (Herlina, 2016).

The foundation of reading literacy is crucial to acquiring knowledge and academic success, as it enables students to master competencies in various subjects (Gershon, 2022). Johnston (1991) emphasized the importance of prior knowledge in reading comprehension, noting that comprehension occurs when students connect new information to what they already know. This idea aligns with the researcher's approach, incorporating relevant portraits to activate students' schemas. Similarly, Cunha and Capellini (2016) described reading comprehension as an intricate process involving word recognition, contextual understanding, drawing conclusions, and linking new information to prior knowledge. The impact of vocabulary instruction on students' cognitive, affective, and behavioral skills has been positive, as both teachers and students recognize the benefits of vocabulary acquisition (Asyiah, 2017). Factors such as language barriers, poor pronunciation, and insecurity contribute to speaking anxiety, highlighting the need for supportive learning environments to mitigate psychological barriers (Rajitha, 2020). A positive educational context, including an engaging curriculum, is essential for reducing these barriers and enhancing language learning (Getie, 2020).

Listening comprehension is another critical component of language learning. Teachers who understand students' listening difficulties can help address these challenges and develop strategies to improve comprehension (Gilakjani et al., 2016). Early exposure to literacy-rich environments, including access to various reading materials, helps foster positive attitudes toward reading and improves language development (Boulhrir, 2017). However, several challenges have been identified in the Philippines, particularly in the context of Grade Six pupils in Sorsogon, where limited vocabulary, poor grammar, and difficulty identifying main ideas hinder reading comprehension (Estremera, 2018). Language immersion and curriculum improvements are necessary to address these challenges, especially as the shift to Distance Learning during the COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated learning gaps. Domingue et al. (2022) found that oral reading fluency declined during the pandemic, highlighting the need for more effective teaching methods and adequate reading materials (Mule, 2014).

The pandemic further disrupted the education system, forcing schools to transition to modular learning, which required greater parental involvement (Caasi & Pentang, 2022). A significant issue during this time was the teacher-to-student ratio, which hindered individualized attention and support for students (Llego, 2014). To overcome these barriers, Ropero (2019) recommended providing students with access to diverse reading materials and teacher-guided practice. The pandemic also led to a noticeable decline in students' reading comprehension abilities, emphasizing the importance of continued collaboration between parents and teachers to address these challenges and support children's development (Ganaden, 2022; Gadiano, 2023).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored in Marie Clay's (1970) Reading Recovery theory and early literacy development, which has been influential in understanding how young children acquire reading skills, particularly through strategies such as phonemic awareness. The theory emphasizes that literacy processing can be challenging for learners due to varying strengths, weaknesses, and individual causes of difficulty. Reading Recovery offers targeted support by addressing foundational gaps in fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension—key components that influence reading literacy. Thus, the theory aligns with this study's goal of identifying factors that affect learners' reading literacy skills, highlighting how struggling readers can benefit from early and intensive intervention.

Objectives

This study generally aimed to determine the degree of factors affecting the reading literacy skills of Junior High School learners in a national high school, District of Salvador Benedicto, Division of Negros Occidental, during the School Year 2023-2024, as the basis for an intervention plan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) is the degree of factors affecting the reading literacy skills of learners in the area of fluency, vocabulary and comprehension; 2) the degree of factors affecting the reading literacy skills of learners when grouped according to the aforementioned variable; and 3) the significant difference in the degree of factors affecting the reading literacy skills of the learners when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Methodology

This section presents a discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design to identify the factors affecting the reading literacy skills of Junior High School learners during the 2023-2024 school year, with the aim of developing an intervention plan. Descriptive research, as explained by McCombes (2019), involves observing and measuring one or more variables through quantitative and qualitative methods, without exploring the reasons behind the phenomena. It focuses on accurately characterizing a population, situation, or phenomenon by answering questions such as what, when, where, who, and how. The researcher found this design most suitable, as it aligns with the study's goal of assessing the current state of reading literacy, comparing variables, exploring potential causes, testing hypotheses, and generating generalizations and theories based on the findings.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study will be the Forty-two (42) Junior High School teachers of Sofronio Carmona Memorial National High School- main campus for the academic year 2023-2024. Total population will be used, and purposive random sampling will be utilized.

Instruments

A researcher-made questionnaire was utilized to collect data on the factors influencing the reading literacy skills of junior high school learners for the 2023-2024 school year, serving as the foundation for an intervention plan. The questionnaire was divided into two sections: Part I focused on the respondents' profile, including age, sex, family income, highest educational attainment, and years of service, while Part II contained 10 items per area, totaling 30 questions. These questions were rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 indicating "always," 4 "often," 3 "sometimes," 2 "seldom," and 1 "never". It was subjected to validity (4.76-excellent) and reliability (0.928-excellent). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

After validating the research questionnaire with the help of three education experts, the researcher conducted a reliability test with 30 teacher-participants from a school not included in the study. The reliability of the questionnaire was then computed, ensuring its suitability for the research. Following the necessary validation and reliability processes, the researcher requested permission from the district supervisor to proceed with the study. The researcher then printed sufficient copies of the data-gathering instrument and prepared them for distribution to the teacher-respondents. With the principal's approval, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaires while adhering to health protocols. Each teacher respondent voluntarily agreed to participate, was informed about the nature of the study, and was assured of confidentiality regarding their responses. Upon completion, the questionnaires were recollected for data analysis.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of factors affecting the reading literacy skills of junior high school learners when respondents are grouped in the areas of fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension.

Objective No. 2 likewise used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of the factors affecting the reading literacy skills of learning when grouped according to the variables.

Objective No. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine whether or not significant differences will exist between the degree of factors affecting reading skills when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Ethical Consideration

To ensure the study was conducted ethically, the researcher followed general ethical guidelines such as respect for people, beneficence, and justice. Using aliases or pseudonyms for their names, the researcher assured the participants of confidentiality by the Data Privacy Act of 2021. The researcher saw the participants as literate, employed adults with no signs of vulnerability. In the researcher's opinion, the study has significant social value in

ensuring the quality of instruction because it values the various perspectives of school principals and presidents of teachers' leagues in the context of the new normal. The participants have the option of not responding to any questions that might in any way distress them because this study is based on their experiences.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that were gathered consistent with its predetermined objectives.

Table 1

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in Fluency

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>		
1. having difficulties in proper pronunciation, pacing, and expression when delivering a speech.	3.88	High Degree
2. are confident and perform better in front of a friendly audience.	3.74	High Degree
3. are hesitant to express themselves even in their own language.	3.64	High Degree
4. are conscious with their grammar when speaking or writing.	3.95	High Degree
5. are afraid of committing mistakes causing them to frequently stutter in front of a large audience.	3.71	High Degree
6. show low motivation and laziness in reading.	3.43	Moderate Degree
7. learn more when teachers model fluent oral reading.	4.00	High Degree
8. join verse choir or choral reading and any other public speaking activities to improve fluency.	3.33	Moderate Degree
9. exhibit stage fright and fear of criticism.	3.74	High Degree
10. prefer oral reading than silent reading.	3.67	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.71	High Degree

Table 1 shows an overall mean of 3.71, interpreted as a "high degree," indicating that respondents generally observed strong fluency development among learners. Item 8 received the lowest mean of 3.33 ("moderate degree"), referring to learners' participation in activities like verse choir or choral reading, while item 7 received the highest mean of 4.00 ("high degree"), highlighting that learners improve more when teachers model fluent oral reading. These results suggest that teacher modeling plays a crucial role in enhancing students' reading fluency. This supports Rochman's (2017) findings that decoding fluency is vital for reading achievement and that teachers should balance accuracy and fluency by adopting diverse instructional approaches, such as blending grammar-translation with communicative methods.

Table 2

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in Vocabulary

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>		
1. can explain the message of the story using their own words.	3.57	High Degree
2. remember words through memorization.	3.81	High Degree
3. use thesaurus and online dictionaries to help enhance their vocabularies.	3.67	High Degree
4. are aware that language is dynamic and that new words are added to the dictionary every day.	3.90	High Degree
5. Understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	3.90	High Degree
6. find it difficult to understand the meaning of a word when introduced the first time around.	4.00	High Degree
7. learn better when there are word games integrated in their lessons as an activity or drill to improve their vocabulary.	3.95	High Degree
8. were able to learn vocabulary better when words are presented with definition or explanation.	4.19	High Degree
9. prefer reading than doing any other activities during their spare time to enhance their vocabulary skills	3.48	Moderate Degree
10. understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	3.69	High Degree

Overall Mean	3.82	High Degree
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As shown in Table 2, the overall mean is 3.82, interpreted as a “high degree,” indicating that learners generally show strong vocabulary development. The lowest mean score of 3.48 (“moderate degree”) was on item 9, where teachers observed that learners preferred other activities over reading during their spare time, while the highest mean of 4.19 (“high degree”) on item 8 indicated that learners learned vocabulary more effectively when definitions or explanations were provided. This suggests that while some students lack intrinsic motivation to read, they respond well to direct instruction. These findings align with Herlina (2016), who emphasized that students with a strong interest in reading tend to have better English vocabulary mastery.

Table 3

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Comprehension

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>		
1. are aware that words have literal and contextual meanings.	3.88	High Degree
2. are familiar with figurative language and idiomatic expressions.	3.69	High Degree
3. read news online and can know which one are authentic or fake news through determining reliable sources.	3.62	High Degree
4. are attentive readers which could be helpful in developing understanding and comprehension.	3.81	High Degree
5. only like to read if the reading selection catches their interests.	4.00	High Degree
6. can comprehend well to the reading selection through the help of teaching aids such as visuals, auditory and etc.	4.05	High Degree
7. are greatly influenced by teachers' motivation.	4.05	High Degree
8. who were supported by parental guidance and follow-ups by parents at home have better comprehension skills.	3.69	High Degree
9. have better retention through familiarization of information rather than memorization.	3.55	High Degree
10. don't enjoy reading activities and prefer other activities.	3.74	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.81	High Degree

As shown in Table 3, the overall mean was 3.81, interpreted as a “high degree,” indicating strong agreement among teachers that certain instructional strategies enhance reading comprehension. The lowest mean score of 3.55, though still a “high degree,” suggests that while learners benefit from familiarization over memorization, it is less emphasized. The highest mean of 4.05 was shared by items highlighting the effectiveness of teaching aids and the impact of teacher motivation. This suggests that learners comprehend reading materials more effectively when aided by visuals and auditory tools, and that teacher motivation plays a crucial role in student engagement. These findings are supported by Ajoke (2017), who noted poor performance among students taught without instructional materials, and by Tursunovich (2022), who emphasized the value of multimedia tools in creating a supportive and engaging learning environment that enhances focus and performance.

Table 4

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Fluency According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. having difficulties in proper pronunciation, pacing, and expression when delivering a speech.	4.05	High Degree	3.73	High Degree
2. are confident and perform better in front of a friendly audience.	3.60	High Degree	3.86	High Degree
3. are hesitant to express themselves even in their own language.	3.45	Moderate Degree	3.82	High Degree
4. are conscious with their grammar when speaking or writing.	4.00	High Degree	3.91	High Degree

5. are afraid of committing mistakes causing them to frequently stutter in front of a large audience.	3.80	High Degree	3.64	High Degree
6. show low motivation and laziness in reading.	3.50	High Degree	3.36	Moderate Degree
7. learn more when teachers model fluent oral reading.	3.85	High Degree	4.14	High Degree
8. join verse choir or choral reading and any other public speaking activities to improve fluency.	3.45	Moderate Degree	3.23	Moderate Degree
9. exhibit stage fright and fear of criticism.	3.95	High Degree	3.55	High Degree
10. prefer oral reading than silent reading.	3.85	High Degree	3.50	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.75	High Degree	3.68	High Degree

Table 4 presents the degree of factors affecting learners' reading literacy in the area of fluency according to teacher age. Younger teachers reported an overall mean of 3.75, while older teachers reported 3.68—both interpreted as a "high degree." The lowest-rated item for both age groups was item no. 3, regarding learners' hesitation to express themselves even in their native language, interpreted as a "moderate degree." Younger teachers identified the highest concern as learners' difficulties in pronunciation, pacing, and expression (mean = 4.05), while older teachers highlighted the importance of teacher modeling in fluent oral reading (mean = 4.14). These findings suggest that younger teachers observe more technical fluency issues, whereas older teachers emphasize the role of instructional modeling. This aligns with Ali et al. (2023), who pointed out that limited English proficiency, diverse accents, and pronunciation differences significantly challenge learners' listening and comprehension skills, especially in acquiring fluency.

Table 5

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Vocabulary According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. can explain the message of the story using their own words.	3.60	High Degree	3.55	High Degree
2. remember words through memorization.	3.95	High Degree	3.68	High Degree
3. use thesaurus and online dictionaries to help enhance their vocabularies.	3.65	High Degree	3.68	High Degree
4. are aware that language is dynamic and that new words are added to the dictionary every day.	3.85	High Degree	3.95	High Degree
5. Understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	4.10	High Degree	3.73	High Degree
6. find it difficult to understand the meaning of a word when introduced the first time around.	4.10	High Degree	3.91	High Degree
7. learn better when there are word games integrated in their lessons as an activity or drill to improve their vocabulary.	4.00	High Degree	3.91	High Degree
8. were able to learn vocabulary better when words are presented with definition or explanation.	4.35	High Degree	4.05	High Degree
9. prefer reading than doing any other activities during their spare time to enhance their vocabulary skills	3.75	High Degree	3.23	Moderate Degree
10. understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	3.90	High Degree	3.50	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.93	High Degree	3.73	High Degree

Table 5 illustrates the degree of factors affecting learners' reading literacy in the area of vocabulary according to teacher age. Younger teachers reported a higher overall mean of 3.93 compared to 3.73 from older teachers, both interpreted as a "high degree." Among younger teachers, the lowest-rated item (mean = 3.60) indicated that learners could explain a story's message using their own words, while older teachers gave the lowest score (mean = 3.23) to students' preference for reading over other activities during spare time—interpreted as "moderate degree." Both age groups identified the same highest-rated item: learners learned vocabulary better when words were presented with definitions or explanations, scoring 4.35 (younger) and 4.05 (older), both rated "high degree." These results suggest that learners benefit more when vocabulary is explicitly taught with clear definitions, and many struggle when such support is lacking. This supports Ehri's (2014) findings that vocabulary acquisition is enhanced when spelling, pronunciation, and meaning are taught together, and that strategies like reading aloud can improve phonological memory and word retention.

Table 6

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Comprehension According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. are aware that words have literal and contextual meanings.	4.05	High Degree	3.73	High Degree
2. are familiar with figurative language and idiomatic expressions.	3.95	High Degree	3.45	Moderate Degree
3. read news online and can know which one are authentic or fake news through determining reliable sources.	3.85	High Degree	3.41	Moderate Degree
4. are attentive readers which could be helpful in developing understanding and comprehension.	4.10	High Degree	3.55	High Degree
5. only like to read if the reading selection catches their interests.	4.10	High Degree	3.91	High Degree
6. can comprehend well to the reading selection through the help of teaching aids such as visuals, auditory and etc.	4.00	High Degree	4.09	High Degree
7. are greatly influenced by teachers' motivation.	4.25	High Degree	3.86	High Degree
8. who were supported by parental guidance and follow-ups by parents at home have better comprehension skills.	3.90	High Degree	3.50	High Degree
9. have better retention through familiarization of information rather than memorization.	3.85	High Degree	3.27	Moderate Degree
10. don't enjoy reading activities and prefer other activities.	3.85	High Degree	3.64	High Degree
Overall Mean	4.00	High Degree	3.65	High Degree

Table 6 presents the factors affecting learners' reading literacy skills in the area of comprehension based on teacher age. Younger teachers reported a higher overall mean of 4.00 compared to 3.65 from older teachers, both interpreted as a "high degree." Among younger teachers, the lowest-rated items (means around 3.85) included learners' ability to identify fake news, preference for activities other than reading, and retention through familiarization—all still rated "high degree." Their highest score of 4.25 was for the item stating that learners are greatly influenced by teacher motivation. In contrast, older teachers rated lowest (mean = 3.27, "moderate degree") the idea that learners retain better through familiarization rather than memorization, while the highest-rated item (mean = 4.09) emphasized the effectiveness of teaching aids in improving comprehension. These results suggest that student motivation and the use of instructional aids play a significant role in enhancing reading comprehension. This aligns with Keller et al. (2017), who emphasized that teachers' motivation and pedagogical skills are essential in fostering student engagement and effective learning, highlighting the importance of instructional design that is both educational and inspiring.

Table 7

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Fluency According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. having difficulties in proper pronunciation, pacing, and expression when delivering a speech.	3.78	High Degree	3.96	High Degree
2. are confident and perform better in front of a friendly audience.	3.89	High Degree	3.63	High Degree
3. are hesitant to express themselves even in their own language.	3.67	High Degree	3.63	High Degree
4. are conscious with their grammar when speaking or writing.	3.89	High Degree	4.00	High Degree

5. are afraid of committing mistakes causing them to frequently stutter in front of a large audience.	3.00	Moderate Degree	4.25	High Degree
6. show low motivation and laziness in reading.	3.06	Moderate Degree	3.71	High Degree
7. learn more when teachers model fluent oral reading.	3.83	High Degree	4.13	High Degree
8. join verse choir or choral reading and any other public speaking activities to improve fluency.	3.28	Moderate Degree	3.38	Moderate Degree
9. exhibit stage fright and fear of criticism.	3.50	High Degree	3.92	High Degree
10. prefer oral reading than silent reading.	3.22	Moderate Degree	4.00	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.51	High Degree	3.86	High Degree

Table 7 presents the degree of factors affecting learners' reading literacy skills in the area of fluency based on sex. Male respondents had an overall mean of 3.51, while female respondents had 3.86, both interpreted as "high degree." Among males, the lowest mean (3.00) was for the item noting that learners stutter due to fear of making mistakes, interpreted as "moderate degree," while the highest (3.89) reflected learners' improved performance in front of a friendly audience. For females, the lowest score (3.38) pertained to learners' lack of participation in public speaking activities like verse choir, while the highest (4.25) also addressed fear of making mistakes and frequent stuttering, both interpreted as "moderate" and "high degree," respectively. These results imply that both male and female respondents observe learners' fear of public speaking and anxiety about making mistakes, which hinders fluency development. This supports Melouah (2013), who found that fear of interaction is a primary cause of speaking anxiety, as many students feel nervous and embarrassed when required to speak in front of others.

Table 8

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Vocabulary According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. can explain the message of the story using their own words.	3.50	High Degree	3.63	High Degree
2. remember words through memorization.	3.67	High Degree	3.92	High Degree
3. use thesaurus and online dictionaries to help enhance their vocabularies.	3.33	Moderate Degree	3.92	High Degree
4. are aware that language is dynamic and that, new words are added to the dictionary every day.	3.72	High Degree	4.04	High Degree
5. understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	3.89	High Degree	3.92	High Degree
6. find it difficult to understand the meaning of a word when introduced the first time around.	3.67	High Degree	4.25	High Degree
7. learn better when there are word games integrated in their lessons as an activity or drill to improve their vocabulary.	3.56	High Degree	4.25	High Degree
8. were able to learn vocabulary better when words are presented with definition or explanation.	3.89	High Degree	4.42	High Degree
9. prefer reading than doing any other activities during their spare time to enhance their vocabulary skills	3.50	High Degree	3.46	Moderate Degree
10. understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	3.50	High Degree	3.83	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.62	High Degree	3.98	High Degree

Table 8 presents the degree of factors affecting learners' reading literacy skills in the area of vocabulary according to sex, with male respondents reporting an overall mean of 3.62 and female respondents 3.98, both interpreted as a "high degree." Among males, the lowest mean (3.33) was for the use of thesaurus and online dictionaries, interpreted as "moderate degree," while the highest mean (3.89 and 4.08) was for understanding unfamiliar words in context and learning better through definitions, the latter interpreted as "high degree." For females, the lowest mean (3.92) was for the same two items (use of resources and understanding through context), both still

interpreted as “high degree,” while the highest mean (4.42) indicated that learners acquire vocabulary more effectively when words are explained or defined. These findings suggest that both male and female respondents observed that learners grasp vocabulary more effectively when unfamiliar words are either used in context or explained clearly. This aligns with Oclarit (2021), who emphasized that using context clues enhances reading comprehension, and consistent modeling of such strategies improves students’ ability to derive meaning from text.

Table 9

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Comprehension According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. are aware that words have literal and contextual meanings.	3.94	High Degree	3.83	High Degree
2. are familiar with figurative language and idiomatic expressions.	3.56	High Degree	3.79	High Degree
3. read news online and can know which one are authentic or fake news through determining reliable sources.	3.61	High Degree	3.63	High Degree
4. are attentive readers which could be helpful in developing understanding and comprehension.	3.89	High Degree	3.75	High Degree
5. only like to read if the reading selection catches their interests.	3.83	High Degree	4.13	High Degree
6. can comprehend well to the reading selection through the help of teaching aids such as visuals, auditory and etc.	3.94	High Degree	4.13	High Degree
7. are greatly influenced by teachers’ motivation.	3.83	High Degree	4.21	High Degree
8. who were supported by parental guidance and follow-ups by parents at home have better comprehension skills.	3.72	High Degree	3.67	High Degree
9. have better retention through familiarization of information rather than memorization.	3.39	Moderate Degree	3.67	High Degree
10. don’t enjoy reading activities and prefer other activities.	3.83	High Degree	3.67	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.76	High Degree	3.85	High Degree

Table 9 presents the degree of factors affecting learners’ reading literacy skills in the area of comprehension according to sex, with male respondents reporting an overall mean of 3.76 and female respondents 3.85, both interpreted as “high degree.” Among males, the lowest mean score (3.39) was for learners’ retention through familiarization rather than memorization, interpreted as “moderate degree,” while the highest mean scores (3.94) were for learners’ awareness of literal and contextual meanings and the effectiveness of teaching aids, both rated as “high degree.” Among female respondents, the lowest mean (3.63) was for learners’ ability to identify authentic news online, while the highest mean (4.21) was for the influence of teacher motivation—both interpreted as “high degree.” These results suggest that male teachers observed comprehension is enhanced by context awareness and learning materials, while female teachers noted that motivation significantly boosts learners’ engagement. This aligns with Macwan (2015), who highlighted the importance of visual aids in fostering critical thinking, imagination, and language skills, emphasizing their role in making learning engaging and effective.

Table 10

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Fluency According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. having difficulties in proper pronunciation, pacing, and expression when delivering a speech.	4.10	High Degree	3.38	Moderate Degree

2. are confident and perform better in front of a friendly audience.	3.90	High Degree	3.38	Moderate Degree
3. are hesitant to express themselves even in their own language.	3.76	High Degree	3.38	Moderate Degree
4. are conscious with their grammar when speaking or writing.	4.03	High Degree	3.77	High Degree
5. are afraid of committing mistakes causing them to frequently stutter in front of a large audience.	3.62	High Degree	3.92	High Degree
6. show low motivation and laziness in reading.	3.62	High Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
7. learn more when teachers model fluent oral reading.	3.90	High Degree	4.23	High Degree
8. join verse choir or choral reading and any other public speaking activities to improve fluency.	3.28	Moderate Degree	3.46	Moderate Degree
9. exhibit stage fright and fear of criticism.	3.86	High Degree	3.46	Moderate Degree
10. prefer oral reading than silent reading.	3.62	High Degree	3.77	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.77	High Degree	3.58	High Degree

Table 10 presents the degree of factors affecting learners' reading literacy skills in the area of fluency according to teachers' highest educational attainment, revealing an overall mean of 3.77 among teachers with lower educational attainment and 3.58 among those with higher educational attainment, both interpreted as a "high degree." For lower-educated teachers, the lowest mean (3.28) was on learners' participation in verse choir or public speaking activities, interpreted as "moderate degree," while the highest (4.10) was on learners' struggles with pronunciation, pacing, and expression during speech delivery, interpreted as "high degree." Meanwhile, among higher-educated teachers, the lowest mean (3.00) was on learners showing low motivation or laziness in reading, and the highest mean (3.92) was on learners being afraid to make mistakes, leading to frequent stuttering in front of a large audience, both interpreted as "moderate" and "high degree," respectively. These results suggest that learners struggle with speech delivery due to lack of proper guidance or fear of making mistakes, not necessarily due to laziness. This aligns with Crizjale v. Ahmad et al. (2021), who found that students' reluctance in class discussions often stems from anxiety, fear of being called on, and pronunciation issues in English.

Table 11

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Vocabulary According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. can explain the message of the story using their own words.	3.62	High Degree	3.46	Moderate Degree
2. remember words through memorization.	3.86	High Degree	3.69	High Degree
3. use thesaurus and online dictionaries to help enhance their vocabularies.	3.48	Moderate Degree	4.08	High Degree
4. are aware that language is dynamic and that new words are added to the dictionary every day.	3.86	High Degree	4.00	High Degree
5. Understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	3.86	High Degree	4.00	High Degree
6. find it difficult to understand the meaning of a word when introduced the first time around.	4.10	High Degree	3.77	High Degree
7. learn better when there are word games integrated in their lessons as an activity or drill to improve their vocabulary.	3.86	High Degree	4.15	High Degree
8. were able to learn vocabulary better when words are presented with definition or explanation.	4.17	High Degree	4.23	High Degree
9. prefer reading than doing any other activities during their spare time to enhance their vocabulary skills	3.62	High Degree	3.15	Moderate Degree

10. understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	3.66	High Degree	3.77	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.81	High Degree	3.85	High Degree

Table 11 presents the degree of factors affecting learners' reading literacy skills in the area of vocabulary according to teachers' highest educational attainment. The overall mean is 3.81 among lower education attained teachers and 3.85 among higher education attained teachers, both interpreted as a "high degree." The lowest mean score among lower-education attained teachers is 3.48 on item no. 3, which states, "As a teacher, I observed my learners use a thesaurus and online dictionaries to help enhance their vocabularies," interpreted as "moderate degree." Among higher-education attained teachers, the lowest mean score is 3.15 on item 9, which states, "As a teacher, I observed my learners prefer reading over other activities during their spare time to enhance their vocabulary skills," also interpreted as "moderate degree." The highest mean scores for both groups are 4.17 and 4.23, found on item no. 8, which states, "As a teacher, I observed my learners were able to learn vocabulary better when words are presented with definitions or explanations," interpreted as "high degree." These results imply that both groups of respondents agree that learners comprehend vocabulary better when teachers provide definitions or use words in context. This aligns with the findings of Rohmatillah (2014), who noted that students face difficulties in vocabulary learning, such as pronunciation, spelling, and choosing the correct meaning of words based on context.

Table 12

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Comprehension According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. are aware that words have literal and contextual meanings.	3.93	High Degree	3.77	High Degree
2. are familiar with figurative language and idiomatic expressions.	3.79	High Degree	3.46	Moderate Degree
3. read news online and can know which one are authentic or fake news through determining reliable sources.	3.69	High Degree	3.46	Moderate Degree
4. are attentive readers which could be helpful in developing understanding and comprehension.	3.83	High Degree	3.77	High Degree
5. only like to read if the reading selection catches their interests.	3.90	High Degree	4.23	High Degree
6. can comprehend well to the reading selection through the help of teaching aids such as visuals, auditory and etc.	3.90	High Degree	4.38	High Degree
7. are greatly influenced by teachers' motivation.	3.97	High Degree	4.23	High Degree
8. who were supported by parental guidance and follow-ups by parents at home have better comprehension skills.	3.83	High Degree	3.38	Moderate Degree
9. have better retention through familiarization of information rather than memorization.	3.52	High Degree	3.62	High Degree
10. don't enjoy reading activities and prefer other activities.	3.97	High Degree	3.23	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.83	High Degree	3.76	High Degree

Table 12 presents the degree of factors affecting learners' reading literacy skills in the area of comprehension according to teachers' highest educational attainment. The overall mean score for lower education attained teachers is 3.83, and 3.76 for higher education attained teachers, both interpreted as a "high degree." Among lower education attained teachers, the lowest mean score is 3.52 on item no. 9, which states, "As a teacher, I observed my learners have better retention through familiarization of information rather than memorization," interpreted as "high degree." The highest mean score is 3.97 on item no. 7, which states, "As a teacher, I observed my learners are greatly influenced by teachers' motivation," and item no. 10, which states, "As a teacher, I observed my learners don't enjoy reading activities and prefer other activities," both interpreted as "high degree." Among higher education attained teachers, the lowest mean score is 3.23 on item no. 10, which states, "As a teacher, I observed my learners don't enjoy reading activities and prefer other activities," interpreted as "moderate

degree." The highest mean score is 4.38 on item no. 6, which states, "As a teacher, I observed my learners can comprehend well the reading selection through the help of teaching aids such as visuals, auditory, etc.," interpreted as "high degree." These results imply that for lower education attained teachers, some learners prefer activities other than reading, but they are motivated when teachers provide encouragement. For higher education attained teachers, learners benefit from effective visual aids that help them comprehend the lesson. This study's findings align with those of Gilakjani and Sabouri (2016), who emphasize that teachers should motivate learners to read diverse materials, recognize comprehension difficulties, and use appropriate teaching strategies to improve reading comprehension.

Table 13

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Fluency According to Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. having difficulties in proper pronunciation, pacing and expression when delivering a speech.	3.78	High Degree	3.96	High Degree
2. are confident and perform better in front of a friendly audience.	3.56	High Degree	3.88	High Degree
3. are hesitant to express themselves even in their own language.	3.39	Moderate Degree	3.83	High Degree
4. are conscious with their grammar when speaking or writing.	3.78	High Degree	4.08	High Degree
5. are afraid of committing mistakes causing them to frequently stutter in front of a large audience.	3.89	High Degree	3.58	High Degree
6. show low motivation and laziness in reading.	3.28	Moderate Degree	3.54	High Degree
7. learn more when teachers model fluent oral reading.	4.17	High Degree	3.88	High Degree
8. join verse choir or choral reading and any other public speaking activities to improve fluency.	2.78	Moderate Degree	3.75	High Degree
9. exhibit stage fright and fear of criticism.	3.78	High Degree	3.71	High Degree
10. prefer oral reading than silent reading.	3.61	High Degree	3.71	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.60	High Degree	3.80	High Degree

Table 13 shows the factors affecting learners' reading literacy skills in the area of fluency, based on teachers' average family monthly income. Lower-income teachers had an overall mean of 3.60, while higher-income teachers had a mean of 3.80, both interpreted as "high degree." Among lower-income teachers, the lowest mean was 2.78 on item 8, about learners participating in public speaking activities, while the highest was 4.17 on item 7, related to teachers modeling fluent reading. Among higher-income teachers, the lowest mean was 3.54 on item 6, regarding low motivation in reading, and the highest was 4.08 on item 4, about learners being conscious of their grammar. These results suggest that lower-income teachers observed learners improving fluency when teachers modeled reading, while higher-income teachers noted that learners were more focused on grammar and feared making mistakes. This aligns with Ahmad, C.V. (2021), who found that students' reluctance to speak in class often stems from nervousness and concerns about pronunciation errors.

Table 14

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Vocabulary According to Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. can explain the message of the story using their own words.	3.39	Moderate Degree	3.71	High Degree
2. remember words through memorization.	3.61	High Degree	3.96	High Degree

3. use thesaurus and online dictionaries to help enhance their vocabularies.	3.44	Moderate Degree	3.83	High Degree
4. are aware that language is dynamic and that, new words are added to the dictionary every day.	3.61	High Degree	4.13	High Degree
5. Understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	4.00	High Degree	3.83	High Degree
6. find it difficult to understand the meaning of a word when introduced the first time around.	3.83	High Degree	4.13	High Degree
7. learn better when there are word games integrated in their lessons as an activity or drill to improve their vocabulary.	4.06	High Degree	3.88	High Degree
8. were able to learn vocabulary better when words are presented with definition or explanation.	4.28	High Degree	4.13	High Degree
9. prefer reading than doing any other activities during their spare time to enhance their vocabulary skills	2.89	Moderate Degree	3.92	High Degree
10. understand better when unfamiliar words are used in a sentence.	3.50	High Degree	3.83	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.66	High Degree	3.95	High Degree

Table 14 examines the factors affecting learners' reading literacy skills in vocabulary, based on teachers' average family monthly income. Lower-income teachers had an overall mean of 3.66, while higher-income teachers had 3.95, both interpreted as "high degree." Among lower-income teachers, the lowest mean was 2.89 on item 9, related to learners preferring reading over other activities to enhance vocabulary, while the highest was 4.28 on item 8, about learners benefiting from vocabulary definitions. For higher-income teachers, the lowest mean was 3.71 on item 1, about learners explaining a story in their own words, and the highest was 4.13 on items 4, 6, and 8, regarding awareness of language change and the importance of word explanations. These findings suggest that lower-income teachers observed learners benefiting from word explanations, while higher-income teachers noted that learners understand vocabulary better when introduced with definitions or examples, though they struggle with new words initially. This supports Marilyn Jager Adams (2021), who argues that vocabulary is key to reading comprehension.

Table 15

Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Comprehension According to Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I observed my learners...</i>				
1. are aware that words have literal and contextual meanings.	3.44	Moderate Degree	4.21	High Degree
2. are familiar with figurative languages and idiomatic expressions.	3.28	Moderate Degree	4.00	High Degree
3. read news online and are able to know which one are authentic or fake news through determining reliable sources.	3.22	Moderate Degree	3.92	High Degree
4. are attentive readers which could be helpful in developing understanding and comprehension.	3.28	Moderate Degree	4.21	High Degree
5. only like to read if the reading selection catches their interests.	3.89	High Degree	4.08	High Degree
6. can comprehend well to the reading selection through the help of teaching aids such as visuals, auditory and etc.	4.06	High Degree	4.04	High Degree
7. are greatly influenced by teachers motivation.	4.11	High Degree	4.00	High Degree
8. who were supported by parental guidance and follow-ups by parents at home have better comprehension skills.	3.44	Moderate Degree	3.88	High Degree
9. have better retention through familiarization of information rather than memorization.	3.33	Moderate Degree	3.71	High Degree
10. don't enjoy reading activities and prefer other activities.	3.61	High Degree	3.83	High Degree

Overall Mean **3.57** **High Degree** **4.00** **High Degree**

Table 15 explores the factors affecting learners' reading literacy skills in comprehension according to average family income. Lower-income teachers had an overall mean of 3.57, while higher-income teachers had 4.00, both interpreted as "high degree." Among lower-income teachers, the lowest mean was 3.22 on item 3, regarding learners identifying fake news online, and the highest was 4.11 on item 7, highlighting the influence of teacher motivation. For higher-income teachers, the lowest mean was 3.71 on item 9, related to retention through familiarization, and the highest was 4.21 on items 1 and 4, focusing on awareness of word meanings and attentiveness in reading. These results suggest that lower-income teachers observe learners being motivated by teachers, while higher-income teachers note that learners are more aware of contextual meanings and attentive in their reading, enhancing comprehension. This aligns with Barasa (2015), who found that lack of teacher motivation negatively impacts learners' performance.

Table 16

Difference in the Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Fluency According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	20	21.30	216.00	0.919	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	22	21.68				
Sex	Male	18	16.14	119.50	0.014	0.05	Significant
	Female	24	25.52				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	29	23.05	143.50	0.219	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	13	18.04				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	18	19.67	183.00	0.400	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	24	22.88				

Table 16 shows that, based on the Mann Whitney U test, there were no significant differences in the factors affecting reading literacy skills in the area of fluency according to age, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income, as their p-values were all greater than 0.05. However, sex was found to have a significant difference, with a p-value of 0.014, indicating that female teachers may have a greater influence on learners' fluency skills. This suggests that fluency skills in learners are more strongly developed by female teachers, likely due to their tendency to be more vocal and expressive. The findings align with Mistar (2014), who states that gender influences the use of various learning strategies, with female learners utilizing them more intensively, which contributes to better speaking abilities.

Table 17

Difference in the Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Vocabulary According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	20	23.23	185.50	0.381	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	22	19.93				
Sex	Male	18	16.25	121.50	0.015	0.05	Significant
	Female	24	24.44				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	29	21.19	179.50	0.805	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	13	22.19				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	18	18.44	161.00	0.158	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	24	23.79				

Table 17 reveals that age, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income, in teaching did not significantly affect the degree of factors influencing learners' vocabulary skills, as their p-values were all greater than 0.05. However, sex was found to be a significant factor with a p-value of 0.015, indicating that male and female teachers employ different teaching strategies, influencing learners' vocabulary development. Female teachers, for example, may use more figures of speech and idiomatic expressions, enhancing learners' vocabulary. This finding aligns with Shadika et al. (2017), who noted that female learners tend to use more vocabulary learning strategies, such as dictionary and note-taking strategies, leading to better vocabulary mastery.

Table 18

Difference in the Degree of Factors Affecting the Reading Literacy Skills of Learners in the Area Comprehension According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	20	25.65	137.00	0.036		Significant
	Older	22	17.73				
Sex	Male	18	19.67	183.00	0.401	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	24	22.88				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	29	21.84	178.50	0.785		Not Significant
	Higher	13	20.73				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	18	16.50	126.00	0.022		Significant
	Higher	24	25.25				

Table 18 shows that age and average family monthly income significantly affect the degree of factors influencing reading comprehension skills, with p-values of 0.036 and 0.022, respectively. Therefore, the hypotheses stating that there is no significant difference based on these variables were rejected. However, sex, and highest educational attainment, were not significant factors, as their p-values were greater than 0.05. The findings suggest that older teachers, with more life experience, may apply different teaching strategies for comprehension, while lower family income can negatively impact a teacher's performance due to financial stress. These results align with Silagi et al. (2014), who noted that age influences comprehension skills, and Oko (2014), who emphasized how teachers' years of experience and low salaries can affect teaching quality.

Conclusions

The analysis revealed that most respondents are senior female teachers with modest educational backgrounds, from high-income groups, and with long teaching experience. The study found that factors affecting reading literacy skills in the areas of fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension were high among junior high school learners. It concluded that teachers significantly influence literacy acquisition, particularly through their motivation and effective use of teaching materials like visual and audio aids. Age and family income were found to significantly impact comprehension skills, while other variables showed no significant difference. The learners' overall reading literacy skills in a fourth-class municipality in Negros Occidental were rated as "High Degree." Based on these findings, recommendations include providing training for teachers, especially in enhancing their teaching strategies and integrating new technologies to better support learners, particularly those in senior positions.

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